

ORGANIZATION OF COMPETITIVE GAMES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Zunnunova Nozima

Teacher of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Komilova Sayyoraxon

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Omonova Nargizaxon

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Yo'ldashaliyeva Shahinabonu

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Olimova Husnida

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10219014>

Annotation. This article will talk about the issues of proper organization of physical education activities in “preschool educational organizations”. It is written to the children about where, for how long, with what tools and in what parts the training is carried out.

Keywords: preschool education, physical education, educational education, activities, games of character, training, wellness.

Action games are originally a product of ancient folk pedagogy. Even in ancient times, families were brought up on the basis of riddles, games, proverbs that teach children from the very first age to resourcefulness, ingenuity, agility, the little ones were taught action games related to the skills of the initial movement. Games like fast saying, counting, counting games, have attracted younger children. As children grow older, they are taught folk games that involve a variety of activities. Game folklore, derived from folk oral creativity, is still practiced today as the most valuable tool even for the fact that it does not lose its artistic beauty, educational significance.

Any game-whether it's creative. Whether it's a didactic, Musical, or action game, still plays an important role in the child's life itself as a means of knowing the world around him.

In the content of action games there will be a material that will give the child knowledge. This material expands his level of knowledge and enriches and clarifies his vision of the universe. Some episodes depicting people, natural phenomena, deeds of animals form the thematic of plot games. These are given by children in the form of conditional games: “travelers”, “readers”, “geese-white birds”, “lying in the Nest” and other games in an idiosyncratic way. However, in order for the child to correctly perceive the world around, despite all the prerequisites, the truthful characteristics of the should be expressed in an

exciting way by the educator at the time of explaining the conditions of the game. Folk games can be taken as an example in this. The play situation in them attracts the child and brings him up. Dialogue-style dialogue that occurs in some games, on the other hand, directly illustrates the characters and their actions.

Games without a plot and based on specific game quests will also have a lot of interesting material. This material develops the general knowledge, thinking of the child, cultivates his ability to achieve moderation.

When conducting action games in preschool educational organizations, it should be selected taking into account the age level of children, physical and physiological development and children's interests. Action games in small groups are held daily. The duration of training should last around 10-15 minutes. Action games are played at different times of the day. Until breakfast in the morning, it is better for the educator to hold games in quiet movements, which are held with an individual or a small group, in order to create a good mood in all children. During a walk after walks, physical education, music training, it is necessary to conduct meaningful, action games that arouse a wide variety of movement activities, as well as game exercises, accompanied by active actions. In large and preparatory groups, it is advisable that the duration of training lasts up to 20 minutes.

In game activities, favorable conditions are created for the development of attention, perception, further clarification of such features as previously formed imagination, concepts, aiming; games help to further develop creative imagination, memory, thinking, contemplative activity. Thus action games serve the mental development of the child.

Figurative thinking is of great importance in improving mental processes in children. Such a method enriches imagination and encourages the creative execution of game actions.

Research conducted by psychologists shows that the child practically absorbs the concept of space as well as the subject activity due to the activity of play, and at the same time the previously generated visions of space become even more refined.

In games, the perception of space through the main forms: bawosita cognition, sensory emotion and through images knowledge, indirect logical thinking, concepts are juxtaposed in forms.

For example, it is required by the child to independently choose the direction of action or choose a certain path according to the game rule, on the one hand, to be able to immediately cope with the game situation and react to it,

while on the other hand, in this game environment, he is required to realize and visualize the actions that he In action game, these two component come with each other. An explanation of the rules of the game by an educator creates an approximate picture in a child; in the same neighborhood, the transformation of the game situation distorts the plan of action in connection with the action of the beginner or the issuance of signals, and assumes an even more complex action from children – to react instantly and act instantly, games: “two Santa Claus”, “magic wand”, “butterfly children”, “monkeys and hunters”, etc.

Such a reaction will show the extent to which children are ready to adapt in the inhospitable in this environment.

In this case, the trainer should help the child. It is necessary to choose a method of action, taking into account the situation, and gradually teach to perform the task set. For example, at the time of learning one game, a child can be offered two different conditions. When one offers a large and limited space, another time a chasing child is required to run away quickly and far, or to avoid showing agility by distracting him at close range, games such as “Chase”, “cunning fox”.

The skill of being able to aim in the surrounding conditions helps to overcome obstacles in the tasks set in the games “dying from the inside of a wreath to the flag”, “Wolf in a blanket”, “brave children”, etc. In doing so, the children will be able to observe the distance based on the ability they have acquired and determine the way to act in certain conditions on their own.

It is especially important to be able to stay focused among children who are spreading in all directions. The action in such conditions, in which the game situation is constantly changing and suddenly requires a reaction, seems to the child incredibly complex. However, in the process of multiple repetitions, older Gruppe children acquire such skill.

Action games teach children the simplest way to get a timed mooring: they correctly perform actions that are said at play time, performed in turn, at first, and then, before that, at all times. Within the time period shown to the children, they learn to complete a play assignment on the signal. For example:” I count to five, you will make flowers from the flags in your hands during this time, come on, who will stand in line before until I hit chirmanda three times”, the children respond with quick action. In such games, the little ones learn to aim, act consistently and do work for a certain period of time.

The content of the Games consists in the situation that occurs in them, as well as the independent wording of the rules of the game, performing the

movement of characters; explaining the place where the children are, the signs of the game and the direction of movement using terms; analyzing the played game-these contribute to the intellectual development of bari children.

The educator carries out the children's experience of acting with his figurative words by influencing the children's imagination, stimulating and rightly guiding the play activities of each child, consisting of creative performance.

References:

1. Рузиматов, Р. Я., Махкамов, Г. М., Отажонова, С. Р., & Турсунова, Ш. А. (2017). Промышленное развитие в Коканде, причины экологических проблем (1956-1975гг.). Высшая школа, (6), 77-78.
2. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.
3. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. (2021). Pedagogical factors of preparation of future teachers of biology for professional-pedagogical activities. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(6), 48-51.
4. Otajonova, S. (2021, July). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND. In Конференции.
5. Otajonova, S. (2021). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1318>. In RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES (No. 18.06).
6. Асқарова, М. А., Отажонова, С. Р., Алимова, М. Б., & Ирматова, М. Д. (2020). READING-INTELLIGENCE AS A CAPACITY-BUILDING TOOL. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(7), 398-402.
7. Rakhimova, G., Narimonova, Z., Otajonova, S., & Abdulxaeva, M. (2019). Stereotypy and poetics of the endemic of recit. Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems, 11(7), 966-969.
8. Norquzieva, D. S., & Abdullaeva, N. R. (2019). PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENCE. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(6), 490-495.
9. Khamidovna, M. I., Seralievna, N. D., & Okhunovna, M. D. (2022). CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND TYPES OF CONFLICTS AMONG MINORS. International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education, 14(7).
10. Seralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 1212-1216.

11. Sheralievna, N. D. (2021). DYNAMICS OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR FORMATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(10), 666-669.
12. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 1212-1216.
13. Norqo'Ziyeva, D. S. (2021). ILK O'SPIRINLARNI KASBGA YO'NALTIRISHNING AYRIM PSIXOLOGIK MASALALARI. *Scientific progress*, 1(6), 1188-1192.
14. Bakhtiyarovich, U. D. (2022). IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF NATIONAL STRATEGIES IN THE PROCESS OF REFORMS IN THE SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL SPHERE OF THE UPDATED UZBEKISTAN. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 99-102.
15. Хамрақулов, З. Й. (2022). Ҳуқуқшунослик фанларини ўқитишда замонавий таълим технологияларидан фойдаланиш. *Pedagog*, 1(3), 314-318.
16. Хамрақулов, З. Й. (2022). Ҳуқуқшунослик фанларини ўқитишда замонавий таълим технологияларидан фойдаланиш. *Pedagog*, 1(3), 314-318.
17. Khamrakulov, Z. (2022). PROBLEMS OF INCREASING LEGAL INFORMATION AND LEGAL LITERACY OF YOUTH. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(16), 4-7.
18. Egamberdiyeva, T. U. A., & Qurbonov, J. A. (2020). Diagnostics of formation and development of intellectual culture among students. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(4), 512-519.
19. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2019). The necessity of developing intellectual culture of students by the subject of philosophy. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 7(12).
20. Qurbonov, J. A. (2019). Social-pedagogical content of intellectually cultural pointh. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 437-442.
21. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2021). The Content and Essence of the Concept of "Intellectual Culture". *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(5), 15-18.
22. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2022). Role Of Philosophy Education In Forming Intellectual Culture In Future Teachers. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(11), 1366-1371.

23. Акмалжонович, Қ. Ж. (2020). ТАЛАБАЛАР ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛ МАДАНИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ФАЛСАФА ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ЖИХАТЛАРИ. Современное образование (Узбекистан), (6 (91)), 42-49.
24. Акмалжонович, Қ. Ж. (2019). Талабалар интеллектуал маданиятини ривожлантиришнинг фалсафий-педагогик жиҳатлари. Современное образование (Узбекистан), (10 (83)), 3-9.
25. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2022). Objective and Subjective Socio-Pedagogical Factors for the Formation of Intellectual Culture in Future Teachers. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(12), 148-151.
26. Юлдашева, М. М. (2017). Жамиятда ёшларнинг турли иллатлардан асрашнинг самарали йўллари. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 59-60.
27. Юлдашева, М. М., & Каршиева, Ш. В. (2017). Ёшларимизнинг маънавий-ғоявий шаклланишида интернетнинг роли. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 58-59.
28. Юлдашева, М. М. (2017). Мамлакатимизда ижтимоий-иқтисодий ва демократик ислохотларнинг амалга оширида миллий ғоя ва миллий тафаккурнинг ўрни. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 56-58.
29. Юлдашева, М. М., & Тобиров, О. К. (2016). РОЛЬ СМИ В ЖИЗНИ ОБЩЕСТВА. Ученый XXI века, 29.
30. Юлдашева, М. М., & Тобиров, О. К. (2016). СЕМЬЯ И ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ДИСЦИПЛИНА ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СИСТЕМЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. Ученый XXI века, 17.
31. Юлдашева, М. М., & Аъзамов, Б. М. (2016). Бузғунчи ва вайронкор ғоялар ва уларнинг характерли хусусиятлар. Молодой ученый, (3-1), 63-64.
32. Юлдашева, М. М., & Каршиева, Ш. В. (2016). Ёшларнинг маънавий-мафкуравий хуружларнинг объектига айланиб қолиши сабаб. Молодой ученый, (3-1), 64-65.
33. Юлдашева, М. М., & Рузиматов, У. С. (2015). РОЛЬ МОЛОДЁЖИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ СИСТЕМЫ ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ИММУНИТЕТА. Ученый XXI века, (12).
34. Urinboyev, D. (2019). Thoughts About Stratagema Of Western And Eastern Thinkers. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(4), 147-151.
35. Bakhtiyorovich, U. D. (2022). Features of the manifestation of strategems and the relationship between them. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 96-100.

36. Bakhtiyarovich, U. D. (2022). IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF NATIONAL STRATEGIES IN THE PROCESS OF REFORMS IN THE SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL SPHERE OF THE UPDATED UZBEKISTAN. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 99-102.
37. Baratbayev, B. B. (2021). Structural Directions Of Modern Concepts Of National Development Models Of Uzbekistan And Russia. The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, 3(01), 15-20.
38. Ravshanov, F., & Baratbaev, B. (2021). Structural Directions of National Development Models of Uzbekistan and Russia. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS, 4(01), 64-67.
39. Baratbaev, B. B. (2020). STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL MODELS OF DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN AND RUSSIA. Journal of Central Asian Social Studies, 1(02), 21-32.
40. Баратбаев, Б. (2020). METHODS OF FORMATION OF MODELS OF NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND RUSSIA. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ КОНСЕНСУС, 1(4).
41. Baratbaev, B. (2020). PROCESSES OF ORGANIZING NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE INDEPENDENT REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION. East European Scientific Journal, 2(11 (63)), 10-13.
42. Баратбаев, Б. (2021). Россия тараққиёт моделини амалга тадбиқ этиш сиёсати ва унинг натижалари. Общество и инновации, 2(1/S), 194-202.
43. Баратбаев, Б. (2021). Политика реализации модели развития России и ее результаты. Общество и инновации, 2(1/S), 194-202.
44. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). HUMAN PHENOMENON IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 40-42.
45. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHY OF THE CONCEPT OF HAPPINESS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 37-39.
46. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF RENE DEKART IN THE WORK "THE FIRST PHILOSOPHY". INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(06), 176-180.

47. Azizjon, M. (2022). COVERAGE OF ISSUES OF RAISING THE SPIRITUALITY OF A PERSON IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF ABU MANSUR MOTORIDI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(5), 422-428.
48. Davronovich, M. A., & Kholmirezayevich, M. I. (2020). THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ITS SOCIO-ECONOMIC AFFECTS. *MODERN VIEWS AND RESEARCH*, 33.

